
IMPLICIT FUNCTION THEOREM FOR FORMAL POWER SERIES

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Abstract

We generalize a result of Furstenberg about the diagonal of bivariate rational fractions and algebraic series, and give a direct proof of an explicit implicit function theorem for formal power series that is valid for all fields, which implies, in particular, a Lagrange inversion formula and a Flajolet-Soria coefficient extraction formula known for fields of characteristic 0.

1. Main Result

We show that the implicit function theorem for formal power series is a direct consequence of a generalization of Furstenberg's theorem about the diagonal of rational functions and algebraic series.

Theorem 1. *Let K be an arbitrary field. If $P(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ are such that $f(0) = 0$, $P(X, f(X)) = f(X)$ and $P'_Y(0, 0) = 0$, then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$*

$$[X^n]f = \sum_{m \geq 1} [X^n Y^{m-1}] (1 - P'_Y(X, Y)) P^m(X, Y).$$

If the characteristic of K is 0, we also have the following form

$$[X^n]f = \sum_{m \geq 1} \frac{1}{m} [X^n Y^{m-1}] P^m(X, Y).$$

Remark 1. The general case can also be deduced from the 0 characteristic case by regarding the coefficients of $f = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} f_i X^i$ as indeterminates and the first formula as an identity in $\mathbb{Z}[f_1, f_2, \dots]$.

Remark 2. The conditions $P(X, f(X)) = 0$ and $f(0) = 0$ imply that $P(0, 0) = 0$. As $P'_Y(0, 0)$ is also 0, the sums in both expressions of $[X^n]f$ are finite.

Remark 3. Similar results in characteristic 0 can be found in [6].

Remark 4. When $P(X, Y) = X\phi(Y)$, where $\phi(X) \in K[[X]]$ and $\phi(0) \neq 0$, we obtain the Lagrange inversion formula

$$[X^n]f = [Y^{n-1}](\phi(X)^n - Y\phi'(X)\phi(X)^{n-1}).$$

If the characteristic of K is 0, we also have the following form:

$$[X^n]f = \frac{1}{n}[Y^{n-1}]\phi(Y)^n.$$

For different proofs of the Lagrange inversion formula in characteristic 0, see [4].

Remark 5. When $P(X, Y)$ is a polynomial in X and Y , we obtain the Flajolet-Soria coefficient extraction formula. See [1], [7] for proofs in characteristic 0. See [5] for a proof for arbitrary fields using Furstenberg’s Theorem.

2. Proof

When K is a field of 0 characteristic, where $P(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ with $f(0) = 0$, the Taylor formula takes the form

$$P(X, Y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} (Y - f(X))^n P_Y^{(n)}(X, f(X)).$$

However, because of the $n!$ in the denominators, we cannot use it in positive characteristic. To make up for this, we define $P_Y^{[m]}(X, Y)$ as an alternative to the m -th partial derivative of P with respect to Y that “absorbs” the factorial. Once this obstacle is circumvented, the Taylor formula works as expected.

Definition 1. Let $P(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$,

$$P(X, Y) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_j(X)Y^j,$$

where $a_j(X) \in K[[X]]$. We define

$$P_Y^{[m]}(X, Y) = \sum_{j=m}^{\infty} \binom{j}{m} a_j(X)Y^{j-m}.$$

for $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proposition 1. *Let K be an arbitrary field. Let $P(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ with $f(0) = 0$. Then*

$$P(X, Y) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (Y - f(X))^m P_Y^{[m]}(X, f(X)). \tag{*}$$

Proof. Let $P(X, Y) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_j(X)Y^j$ with $a_j(X) \in K[[X]]$ for $j \in \mathbb{N}$. We prove that for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the coefficients of Y^k in the left side and the right side of (*) are equal. Indeed, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & [Y^k] \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (Y - f(X))^m P_Y^{[m]}(X, f(X)) \\ &= \sum_{m=k}^{\infty} \binom{m}{k} (-f(X))^{m-k} \sum_{j=m}^{\infty} \binom{j}{m} a_j(X) f(X)^{j-m} \\ &= \sum_{j=k}^{\infty} a_j(X) f(X)^{j-k} \sum_{m=k}^j \binom{j}{m} \binom{m}{k} (-1)^{m-k} \\ &= \sum_{j=k}^{\infty} a_j(X) f(X)^{j-k} \sum_{m=k}^j \binom{j}{j-m, m-k, k} (-1)^{m-k} \\ &= a_k(X). \end{aligned}$$

We have the last equality because $\sum_{m=k}^j \binom{j}{j-m, m-k, k} (-1)^{m-k} = 1$ if $j = k$ and 0 if $j > k$. This is because we have the multinomial expansion

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b + c)^j &= \sum_{k \leq m \leq j} \binom{j}{j-m, m-k, k} a^{j-m} b^{m-k} c^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{m=k}^j \binom{j}{j-m, m-k, k} a^{j-m} b^{m-k} c^k. \end{aligned}$$

When we take $a = 1, b = -1$, the identity becomes

$$c^j = \sum_{k=0}^j \left(\sum_{m=k}^j \binom{j}{j-m, m-k, k} (-1)^{m-k} \right) c^k.$$

Seeing this as a polynomial identity in the variable c gives us the desired result. □

The following corollary is immediate.

Corollary 1. *Let K be an arbitrary field. Let $Q(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ be such that $f(0) = 0$ and $Q(X, f(X)) = 0$. Then there exists $R(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ such that $Q(X, Y) = (Y - f(X))R(X, Y)$.*

Definition 2. For the formal power series in $K((X_1, \dots, X_m))$

$$P(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m) = \sum_{n_i > -\mu} a_{n_1 n_2 \dots n_m} X_1^{n_1} X_2^{n_2} \dots X_m^{n_m}$$

its (principal) diagonal $\mathcal{D}f(t)$ is defined as the element in $K((T))$

$$\mathcal{D}P(T) = \sum a_{nn\dots n} T^n.$$

In [3], Furstenberg proved the following result about algebraic series and the diagonal of rational fractions.

Proposition 2. (Furstenberg) *Let K be an arbitrary field. Let $Q(X, Y) \in K[X, Y]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ be such that $f(0) = 0$, $Q(X, f(X)) = 0$ and $Q'_Y(0, 0) \neq 0$, then*

$$f(X) = \mathcal{D} \left(Y^2 \frac{Q'_Y(XY, Y)}{Q(XY, Y)} \right).$$

Proposition 2 can be used to deduce a coefficient extraction formula for algebraic series with coefficients in an arbitrary field (see Remark 5) and can be used to compute efficiently the n -th term of an algebraic series with coefficients in a field of positive characteristic [2].

The following proposition is a generalization of Proposition 2, where $Q(X, Y)$ can be any formal power series and not just a polynomial. The only difference in the proof is in the first step where we use Corollary 1 to factorize $Q(X, Y)$.

Proposition 3. *Let K be an arbitrary field. Let $Q(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$ and $f(X) \in K[[X]]$ be such that $f(0) = 0$, $Q(X, f(X)) = 0$ and $Q'_Y(0, 0) \neq 0$. Then*

$$f(X) = \mathcal{D} \left(Y^2 \frac{Q'_Y(XY, Y)}{Q(XY, Y)} \right).$$

Proof. Using Corollary 1 we can write $Q(X, Y) = (Y - f(X))R(X, Y)$ with $R(X, Y) \in K[[X, Y]]$. We have $R(0, 0) \neq 0$ because $f(0) = 0$ and $Q'_Y(0, 0) \neq 0$. Then

$$\frac{1}{Q(X, Y)} Q'_Y(X, Y) = \frac{1}{Y - f(X)} + \frac{R'_Y(X, Y)}{R(X, Y)}.$$

Replacing X by XY and multiplying by Y^2 we get

$$\mathcal{D} \left(Y^2 \frac{Q'_Y(XY, Y)}{Q(XY, Y)} \right) = \mathcal{D} \left(\frac{Y^2}{Y - f(XY)} \right) + \mathcal{D} \left(Y^2 \frac{R'_Y(XY, Y)}{R(XY, Y)} \right). \quad (\dagger)$$

For the first term on the right side of (†) we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{D}\left(\frac{Y^2}{Y - f(XY)}\right) \\ &= \mathcal{D}\left(\frac{Y}{1 - Y^{-1}f(XY)}\right) \\ &= \mathcal{D}\left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y^{-n+1}f(XY)^n\right) \\ &= \mathcal{D}(f(XY)) \\ &= f(X). \end{aligned}$$

For the second term, as $R(0, 0) \neq 0$, $\frac{R'_Y(XY, Y)}{R(XY, Y)}$ is a power series in XY and Y , so when we multiply this by Y^2 there is no diagonal term. □

Proof of Theorem 1. Let the power series $Q(X, Y)$ be defined as $Q(X, Y) = P(X, Y) - Y$, then $Q'_Y(0, 0) = P'_Y(0, 0) - 1 \neq 0$, and $Q(X, f(X)) = P(X, f(X)) - f(X) = 0$. According to Proposition 3,

$$\begin{aligned} f &= \mathcal{D}\{Y^2 Q'_Y(XY, Y)/Q(XY, Y)\} \\ &= \mathcal{D}\{Y^2(P'_Y(XY, Y) - 1)/(P(XY, Y) - Y)\} \\ &= \mathcal{D}\{Y(1 - P'_Y(XY, Y))/(1 - \frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y})\} \\ &= \mathcal{D}\{Y(1 - P'_Y(XY, Y))(1 + \sum_{m \geq 1} (\frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y})^m)\}. \end{aligned}$$

We have the last equality due to the fact that $P'_Y(0, 0) = 0$, $\frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y}$ has no constant term, and therefore $1/(1 - \frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y}) = 1 + \sum_{m \geq 1} (\frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y})^m$. As in each term of $Y(1 - P'_Y(XY, Y))$ the power of Y is larger than that of X , it cannot contribute to the diagonal. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} f_n &= [X^n Y^n] Y(1 - P'_Y(XY, Y))(1 + \sum_{m \geq 1} (\frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y})^m) \\ &= [X^n Y^n] Y(1 - P'_Y(XY, Y))(\sum_{m \geq 1} (\frac{P(XY, Y)}{Y})^m) \\ &= \sum_{m \geq 1} [X^n Y^{m-1}] (1 - P'_Y(X, Y)) P(X, Y)^m. \end{aligned}$$

□

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